

originated from Lebanon, showing symptoms of leaf mottling and vein yellowing. The virus, whose particles were observed with electron microscopy from a partially purified preparation and in tissue thin sections, was provisionally named Mulberry badnavirus-1 (MBV-1). Since different attempts of completing the full-length genome sequence through a conventional approach failed, a small RNA library was constructed for deep sequencing and run according to Illumina protocol.

sRNAs analysis allowed the design of a set of primers used in PCR for the achievement of the full length sequence. The complete genome contains all the sequence features and the characteristic functional domains of the genus *Badnavirus* (highest nucleotide similarity shared with FBV-1 at 54%). By contrast to the badnaviruses, with genomes encoding for 3-4 ORFs, MBV-1 resembles genome organization of *Petunia vein clearing virus* (PVCV), which bears a single ORF.

The study of the distribution of sRNA on the MBV-1 complete genome showed a tidy prevalence of 21- and 22-nt reads, differently from other viruses in the *Caulimoviridae* family, featuring a nuclear replication and typically supporting an accumulation of the 24-nt sRNAs involved in methylation processes.

EVIDENCES OF THE EXISTENCE OF GRAPEVINE PINOT GRIS VIRUS ISOLATES SHOWING DIVERSE PATHOGENICITY. M. Morelli¹, A. Giampetruzzi¹, P. Bianchedi², P. Saldarelli¹, V. Gualandri². ¹Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante del C.N.R. UOS Bari, Via Amendola, 165/A, 70126 Bari, Italy. ²FEM-IASMA, Centre for Technology Transfer, via E. Mach, 1 38010, San Michele all'Adige (TN) Italy E-mail: p.saldarelli@ba.iov.cnr.it

Grapevine Pinot gris virus (GPGV) is a recently described trichovirus, discovered by next generation sequencing (NGS) in the cv Pinot gris, seemingly associated to a new grapevine disease. To define the aetiology of the disease, the virome of two additional Pinot gris accessions, showing or not symptoms, were analysed by NGS. Virus content consistently reproduced the already known virome with GPGV, *Grapevine rupestris stem pitting virus* (GRSPaV), *Grapevine Rupestris vein feathering virus* (GRVfV) and the two viroids *Hop stunt viroid* (HSVd) and *Grapevine yellow speckle viroid 1* (GYSVd-1), infecting either the symptomatic or the symptomless plants. Whole genome phylogenetic analysis on seven GPGV isolates, including three isolates originating from Czech Republic and Slovak Republic and consensus sequences assembled by NGS, clearly clustered those infecting symptomatic vines. We therefore extended the analysis to two genomic regions, comprising the RNA polymerase RNA dependent domain of the replicase gene and part of the movement protein, on a group of accessions from Trentino, free from relevant viruses involved in leafroll, infectious degenerations and rugose-wood associated grapevine diseases. Maximum likelihood and Bayesian phylogenetic analyses of nucleotide sequences, proved that isolates from vines with symptoms form a clade distinct from those of symptomless vines, thus confirming studies on the whole genome. These results showed that GPGV virus populations from Trentino underwent, in the infected vines, a different evolutionary dynamic, not related with the vine variety, which selected for isolates with different pathogenicity.

VALIDATION OF A RAPID AND SENSITIVE DIAGNOSTIC PROTOCOL FOR THE IDENTIFICATION OF PLUM POX VIRUS: LAMP RT-PCR. G. Pasquini¹, L. Ferretti¹, S. Lopriore², G. Airoldi², M. Barba¹. ¹Consiglio per la Ricerca e la sperimentazione in Agricoltura – Centro di Ricerca per la Patologia Vegetale

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The development of innovative rapid and reliable detection methods ‘ready to use’ directly in open field or at the borders, is an important aspect for the phytosanitary control of quarantine pathogens as *Plum pox virus* (PPV), a virus negatively impacting on stone fruits cultivation.

The use of the rapid and sensitive loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) technology with a portable device allows to perform the analysis directly in the field, combining the sensitivity of the technique with a practical use for a rapid interception of pathogens.

A commercial kit for the diagnosis of PPV based on LAMP technology (Bioteltec) has been validated by the calculation of the performance criteria (ISO 17025) compared with those obtained for a real time RT-PCR in a national Italian ringtest. All experiments were performed with a Bioteltec commercial kit and the Genie® II Instrument (Optigene Ltd.), starting from total RNAs (TRNA) extracted from target and no-target reference samples by a simple and rapid extraction kit (Bioteltec) and by RNeasy Plant minikit (Qiagen).

LAMP RT-PCR resulted to be a very efficient and rapid technology for PPV detection, showing a higher analytical sensitivity than RT-PCR, both with sensitive or rapid TRNA extraction methods, with a comparable diagnostic accuracy and repeatability, resulting very useful for the diagnosis of the virus, also directly in the field.

DRAFT GENOMES OF AN ITALIAN STRAIN OF PSEUDOMONAS SAVASTANOI PV. SAVASTANOI AND OF TWO ENDOPHYTES LIVING IN THE OLIVE KNOTS. C. Moretti¹, C. Cortese¹, D. Passos da Silva², G. DeVescovi², E. Torelli³, C. Ramos⁴, V. Venturi², G. Firrao³, R. Buonauro¹. ¹Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari e Ambientali, Università di Perugia, Via Borgo XX Giugno 74 – 06121- Perugia, Italy. ²Centre for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, Trieste, Italy. ³Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie e Ambientali, Università degli Studi di Udine, Udine, Italy. ⁴Área de Genética, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Málaga, Instituto de Hortofruticultura Subtropical y Mediterránea “La Mayora” (IHSM-UMA-CSIC), Málaga, Spain. E-mail: chiara.moretti@unipg.it

Knots caused by *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* in olive trees provide an interesting niche for studying bacterial multispecies interactions. Among the high number of bacterial endophytes detected inside the olive knots by metagenomics, those belonging to the genera *Pantoea*, *Pectobacterium*, *Erwinia* and *Curtobacterium* are the most represented. Our attention is focused on two endophytic bacterial species, *Pantoea agglomerans* and *Erwinia oleae*, which cause an increase in disease severity when co-inoculated with *P. savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* in olive plants. To better understand the molecular basis of the interaction between the pathogen and the endophytes, we sequenced their genomes. The comparison of the *P. savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* genome with that of the previously sequenced strain NCPPB 3335 provides useful information to explain the different extend of virulence the two strains show. In the *E. oleae* genome, the quorum sensing system is present and knockout mutants of *luxI/R* genes homologs were obtained. We are verifying whether *E. oleae* undergoes inter-species communication with *P. savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* through this system. *In silico* analysis of *P. agglomerans* genome reveals the presence of a complete *hrp/hrc* gene cluster, which explains the capability of this strain to induce hypersensitive reaction in tobacco plants. This cluster shows remarkable synteny and high sequence similarity with *Erwinia amylovora* and *Erwinia pyrifoliae* homologs. Mutants of *hrpN*, *hrpY* and *hrpJ* genes were obtained and their phenotypes will be described.